

Integrated pest management—weeds

Evaluation of herbicides for transplanted rice (TPR) in Kerala, India

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We evaluated 16 weed control treatments using six preemergence herbicides and hand weeding during kharif (monsoon, Jun-Oct) 1989 and rabi (wet season, Nov-Mar) 1989–90 for chemical weed control in TPR.

The field experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. MO-6 rice (115 d) was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing in a silty clay lowland. Urea, Mussoorie rock phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha: N and K were applied in two equal splits at planting and 30 d after transplanting (DT), and P was applied fully as basal.

Herbicides were applied on a thin film of water 3 or 7 DT as per treatment. Weeds were hand-removed at fortnightly intervals until 45 DT in weed-free check (WFC) and at 20 and 40 DT in hand weeding twice (HWT).

Weeds at 55 DT were 22% grasses, 44% sedges, and 34% broadleaf weeds. Important species were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Tragus* sp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *C. halpan*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Juncus* spp., *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Limnocharis flava*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *L. adscendens*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Sphenoclea zeylmica*, *Lobelia alsinoides*, and *Lindernia rotundifolia*.

All herbicides except thiobencarb significantly reduced weed growth compared with the unweeded control and were statistically comparable to the WFC and HWT treatments (see table). Treatments significantly affected rice yields, but there was no significant interaction between seasons and treatments.

Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl 0.005 and 0.01 kg 7 DT and pretilachlor 1.25 kg

Effect of weed control treatments on TPR. Kerala, India, 1989-90.

Treatment	Dose ^a (kg ai/ha)	Time (DT)	Weed dry wt (g/m ²)	Mean rice yields (t/ha)		Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit of weed control (\$/ha)	cost of weed control (\$/ha)	Marginal benefit-cost ratio
				Grain	Straw				
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.005	3	106.1	3.0	4.3	618	184	—	—
Pyrdzosulfuron-ethyl	0.005	7	70.9	3.3	4.7	677	243	—	—
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.01	3	79.8	3.1	4.6	645	211	—	—
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.01	7	81.8	3.3	4.7	682	248	—	—
Pretilachlor	0.75	3	53.4	3.1	4.4	640	206	11.8	17.5
Pretilachlor	0.75	7	84.1	3.0	4.2	621	187	11.8	15.8
Pretilachlor	1.25	3	75.0	3.3	4.7	676	242	18.3	13.2
Pretilachlor	1.25	7	110.7	3.2	5.0	658	224	18.3	12.2
Anilophos	0.40	7	85.7	3.2	4.5	652	218	13.6	16.0
Anilophos	0.60	7	82.0	3.1	4.6	648	214	19.4	11.0
Oxadiazon	0.40	7	79.2	3.1	4.4	633	199	15.6	12.8
Tridiphane	0.40	7	101.6	2.8	4.1	583	149	25.9	5.8
Thiobencarb	1.00	7	121.4	2.9	4.4	595	161	24.0	6.7
Weed-free check	—	—	65.6	3.5	4.8	730	296	92.4	3.2
Hand weeding twice	—	—	74.7	3.4	4.8	693	259	64.6	4.0
Unweeded control	—	—	175.8	2.1	2.9	434	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	—	—	60.3	0.3	0.6	—	—	—	—

^aai = active ingredient. Cost of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl 10 WP not available; pretilachlor 50 EC, \$6.5/liter; anilophos 30 EC, \$8.7/liter; oxadiazon 25 EC, \$8.5/liter; tridiphane 48 EC, \$28.67/11ter; thiobencarb 10 G, \$2.2/kg; hand weeding, \$1.42/person per d; rice grain, \$200/t; straw, \$5/t.

3 DT had grain yields and gross returns equal to that of the WFC. Herbicide treatments pretilachlor (0.75 kg) and

anilophos (6.4 kg ai/ha) were more economic than hand weeding according to marginal benefit-cost ratio. □

Evaluation of Bromadiolone in irrigated ricefields

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We studied a single-dose anticoagulant rodenticide to establish the suitable

period for poison baiting.

Bandicota bengalensis, *Millardia meltada*, and *Mus booduga* considerably damage rice fields of Tanjore District, Tamil Nadu. Seven plots (0.5 km²) were treated with bromadiolone 0.005% wax cakes (burrow baiting) at 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). Reference plots were also maintained.

Live burrows and percent successful control of rodents by using bromadiolone 0.005% wax cake during various rice growth stages.

Treatment (d after transplanting)	Tiller damage (%)	Live burrows ^a (no./ha)											
		<i>B. bengalensis</i>			<i>M. meltada</i>			<i>M. booduga</i>			Total		
		I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)
20	2.1	12.0	0.8	93.3	2.4	0.8	66.7	3.2	0.8	75.0	17.6	2.4	86.4
30	4.4	13.6	0.8	94.1	4.8	1.6	66.7	7.2	1.6	77.8	25.6	4.0	84.4
40	7.0	18.4	1.6	91.3	4.0	0.8	80.0	10.4	3.2	69.2	31.2	5.6	87.2
50	2.5	16.8	4.0	81.0	8.0	0.8	90.0	12.0	4.0	66.7	36.8	8.8	78.3
60	3.4	20.0	4.0	80.0	11.2	4.8	57.1	13.6	4.8	64.7	44.8	13.6	69.6
70	5.2	24.0	11.2	53.3	9.6	4.0	58.3	16.8	5.0	76.2	50.4	19.2	61.9
Reference plot (mean)	9.4	20.0	—	—	8.8	—	—	7.2	—	—	36.0	—	—

^aI = pretreatment, II = posttreatment.